

Human Accountability towards Ecosystem: An Ethical Constructive Study

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Abstract: *The ecosystem is a system where living and non-living components interact through energy flow and nutrient cycles. Humans, as the only self-aware moral agents in this system, have an ethical duty to keep ecological balance. This paper looks at human responsibility toward the ecosystem by examining both anthropocentric and non-anthropocentric ethical views. While anthropocentrism values nature only for human benefit, extreme non-anthropocentric perspectives often overlook important human needs. To resolve this ethical conflict, the study highlights Aldo Leopold's Land Ethic as a useful and broad approach. Leopold's framework acknowledges the intrinsic value of the living community while respecting the legitimate needs of human life. The paper argues that moral responsibility should include preserving the integrity, stability, and sustainability of the ecosystem as a whole. Given the issues of environmental damage, climate change, and fairness for future generations, the study stresses the importance of ecological awareness for achieving a balanced and sustainable future.*

Keywords: Ecosystem, Environmental Ethics, Anthropocentrism, Aldo Leopold, Human Responsibility, Sustainability

Introduction - *“An ecosystem is a geographic area where plants, animals and other organisms, as well as weather and landscape, work together to form a bubble of life.”*¹ (“Ecosystem”) An ecosystem can be huge, such as a large forest or lake, or it can be small, such as a puddle of water or a rotting log. *“An ecosystem can be categorized into its abiotic constituents, including minerals, climate, soil, water, sunlight, and all other nonliving elements, and its biotic constituents, consisting of all its living members. Linking these constituents together are two major forces: the flow of energy through the ecosystem, and the cycling of nutrients within the ecosystem.”*² (“Ecosystem | Definition”) The term ‘Ecosystem’ was coined by A.G. Tansley in 1935. Therefore, an ecosystem cannot simply be described as a "bubble of life"; it must be defined as a structural and functional unit of nature, where the biotic components (living organisms) and their abiotic environment (non-living components) are constantly engaged in mutual interaction. In 1935, Arthur George Tansley used the term 'ecosystem' to demonstrate that living organisms and their physical environment together form a unified, dynamic system, where energy flow and nutrient cycles bind the entire system together. From this perspective, 'ecology' is no longer the study of isolated plants and animals, but rather the science of the structure and function of the entire ecosystem—that is, the interdependent relationship between living and non-living components; and we, as human beings, are not outside this ecosystem, but merely a part of this system.³ (“Ecosystem Structure and Functions”) And the relation between the natural environment and the world of living things and studies and research related to those is called Ecology. Ernst Haeckel coined the word ‘ecology’ in 1866. The term has derived from two Greek words: ‘aeiko’ and ‘logos’; ‘oikos’ meaning ‘house’ and ‘logos’ meaning ‘science’. So, Ecology is the ‘study of the household of nature’. And when ecology is concerned with understanding the interconnectedness of nature's "household system" or family structure, fundamental questions of environmental ethics—regarding responsibility, rights, and moral accountability—arise from this reality.

Every living thing in the ecosystem is dependent on one another in a food-consumer relationship. We can construct an imaginary pyramid of the ecosystem based on this relationship, which is called the ecological pyramid. So ecological pyramid is “a graphical representation designed to show the biomass or productivity of each trophic level in a particular ecosystem.”⁴ (Liwayway Memije-Cruz) The use of Ecological Pyramids was first described by Charles Elton in 1927. These types of quantitative diagrams are generally divided into three categories—the pyramid of numbers, the pyramid of biomass, and the pyramid of energy—each of which represents the different trophic levels or steps of the food chain.

(Source-“Lesson 4.” Biology, 2025, <https://schsbio.weebly.com/lesson-4.html> Accessed 5 Dec. 2025.)

From the perspective of energy flow, it is observed that on average, only about 10% of the energy is transferred from one trophic level to the next; the remaining energy is used by the organism for its own survival, growth, and reproduction, and is lost to the environment as heat. This is why the upper levels of the pyramid have comparatively fewer organisms and less biomass, and they are entirely dependent on the producers and lower-level consumers of the broader levels below.^{5(PMF IAS)} If there occurs a change in any of the stages of the pyramid or there is a crisis in the

elements of that stage, the whole pyramid structure will breakdown. This kind of relation of dependency has been going on since the Earth's beginning. Even though humans did not exist in the beginning, they have secured the apex spot of the pyramid today.

Currently, humans are the ideal and only self-conscious entity in the ecosystem among all others. So, the issue of ethics comes up with every human activity. Now the question arises as to what extent humans have the right to enjoy the other elements of the ecosystem? In other words, we can ask if the world of ethics is only about humans. Is the sphere of ethical discourse limited only to humans? Based on the questions raised, we get two kinds of views: first, anthropocentric and second, non-anthropocentric. According to the anthropocentric view, humans are the most important and the central characters of this ethical world. According to Hebrew ideology and Greek philosophical views, the human being is the receptacle of the ethical world. That is why it is said in the cosmology of the Old Testament – God sent his son as a human being and conferred on him the supremacy of the world – ‘dominance over aquatic fish, over the ethereal bird, over all the terrestrial creatures. God intended that aquatic fish, ethereal birds and all the terrestrial creatures would be afraid and obey man as their master. Aristotle says that “*everything has evolved according to human needs.*”⁶(Bhattacharya 194) Aristotle further says, “*Plants exist for the sake of animals, and brute beasts for the sake of man, domestic animals for his use and food, wild ones (or at any rate most of them) for food and other accessories of life, such as clothing and various tools. Since nature makes nothing purposeless or in vain, it is undeniably true that she has made all animals for the sake of man.*”⁷(Singer 267) In environmental ethics, the 'anthropocentric' perspective primarily refers to a human-centered value system, where moral status and intrinsic value are recognized only in humans, while the rest of nature—plants, animals, rivers, or mountains—is generally considered merely as instrumental resources for human well-being. Britannica, therefore, defines anthropocentrism as a doctrine in which humanity is considered

superior to nature, and non-human entities are viewed as 'resources' subject to legitimate exploitation by humans.^{8(mpetruzzello)}

Contemporary discussions also distinguish between “strong” and “weak” or “enlightened anthropocentrism.” In its strong sense, anthropocentrism views nature merely as a resource to be used for fulfilling immediate human needs; however, “enlightened anthropocentrism,” by considering the long-term consequences of environmental destruction—health risks, resource scarcity, climate change, etc.—argues that protecting nature becomes a moral imperative even from an anthropocentric ethical perspective.^{9(“Anthropocentric Worldview”)} That is, although the argument for protecting nature is ultimately expressed in terms of the well-being of humanity and future generations, in practice, it supports environmentally friendly policies and behaviors.

On the other hand, according to the non-anthropocentric view, other elements of the ecosystem are recognized along with humans. It is said here that, if all forms of colonialism and imperialism are condemnable, then humans will only spread their empire, denying everything non-human for their self-gain, which is equally condemnable. The core tenet of non-anthropocentric value theory is that moral status and intrinsic value are not limited to humans alone; some non-human entities are also worthy of consideration for their own sake. Within this framework, several sub-perspectives can be found:

- (a) Biocentric views (such as Paul Taylor's Respect for Nature) where all living beings are considered to have equal intrinsic worth;
- (b) Eco-centric/holistic doctrines, which consider not only individual organisms but also entire ecosystems, species populations, and landscapes as part of the moral community;
- (c) And rights-based animal ethics, which recognizes the individual rights of at least sentient animals.

So, we should go beyond anthropocentric doctrine and adopt non-anthropocentrism. It should be possible only when we would consider nature to be autonomously precious and would admit its ethical standpoint. So, it is impertinent to air the feelings of selfishness if we try to bridge our ethical relationship with nature. We should not destroy nature as all elements that belonged to it have their merit of existence and individual purpose. We would accomplish our duty towards nature in accordance with its intrinsic value. However, if a non-anthropocentric stance reaches the point where even the slightest harm to every plant and animal is considered morally impermissible, then the fundamental processes of human life—eating, farming, disease control, etc.—all become ethically problematic. This difficulty is what many consider to be the practical unfeasibility of an extreme biocentric or eco-centric viewpoint that assigns equal intrinsic value to everything.

Neither of the above-mentioned theories can be accepted unanimously. Contemporary ethics recognize that our duties and non-duties cannot be determined based only on a human perspective. This anthropocentric view introduces an ego-logical perspective, not an eco-logic alone. Here humans are the rulers of the pyramid, because of which that ecosystem becomes unsustainable, dualistic, imbalanced and mechanistic also. Again, the non-anthropocentric view cannot be accepted as well because, if every element in nature is seen to have value for itself, killing of animals or destroying vegetation would be strictly prohibited and thereby there would occur an imbalance in nature. Thus, while on the one hand, an exclusively anthropocentric approach grants humans the 'right' to stand at the top of the ecosystem pyramid and exploit and destroy all other levels at will, on the other hand, many non-anthropocentric positions become practically impossible to implement in real life. Recent discussions on environmental ethics suggest the need for a position somewhere between these two extremes, where the intrinsic value of nature is acknowledged, while the practical needs and responsibilities of humanity are also considered rationally; Aldo Leopold's land ethic is considered a powerful example of this middle ground.

So, to get out of this problem, we need a different solution, a different perspective, according to which these feet recognize the innate value within natural elements, the anthropocentric values within those elements will be acknowledged. Aldo Leopold has spoken about exactly this.

American materialist Aldo Leopold has spoken about including the elements of nature including the world of plants and animals, in another world the ecosystem into the sphere of ethics. We can take Leopold's theory as neither anthropocentric nor non-anthropocentric. In Environmental ethics, anthropocentric theory analyses the natural elements from the point of view of their utility to humans. But Leopold has approached the natural elements from a Holistic point of view. Many calls Leopold's theory non-anthropocentric but there are some significant differences with non-anthropocentric doctrines. Aldo Leopold's land ethics described ecosystems as living organisms; they did not completely ban the killing of animals or the cutting of plants. Despite acknowledging the intrinsic value of the various entities of nature, he did not deny the extrinsic value of nature for human welfare. In this context, Zardins has said that *"If we take Leopold's ecosystem as a whole, we can sometimes speak about the supplementary values of the biotic entities when discussing them logically."*^{10(Khanam 21)} Therefore, Leopold's land ethic can be called "eco-centric" on the one hand, because it primarily takes the health of the entire biotic community as its moral standard and places humanity's position within that community. On the other hand, he does not completely disregard human welfare, economic needs, and practical land management; rather, he attempts to strike a balance between what is morally and aesthetically right and what is economically advantageous. For this reason, many have interpreted Leopold's land ethic not as strictly non-anthropocentric, but rather as a kind of "ecological" middle ground that transcends the limitations of both anthropocentric and non-anthropocentric perspectives. The responsibility and liability that we have for the whole, we have the same for the parts. We have to invest our ethical responsibilities not only in the human world but also in the

natural world. So, we have to give nature its own due value for itself and only use its values for human beings, the little that we need. We can also say that Aldo Leopold's land ethics theory introduces an eco-logical approach; where the ecosystem will be stable, holistic, sustainable, and balanced.

(Source - Chase, C. (2014, November 22). *Systems Thinking: Seeing How Everything is Connected*. Creative by Nature; Creative by Nature.

<https://creativesystemstinking.wordpress.com/2014/11/22/systems-thinking-seeing-how-everything-is-connected/>)

But, today, we are exploiting nature based on anthropocentric views. Therefore, the ecosystem is under threat today and with that making, the future generation comes at the verge of imminent destruction. In this context, Leopold has said that "*In nature, man-made changes neglect the resistant power of living things. Man is constantly changing the environment. Nature can bear with the destructions that happen due to changes in nature, itself. But a complete change is catastrophic for nature*".¹¹ (Khanam 17) Ecosystem and biodiversity are being harmed because of

our inhuman affairs towards nature, which is unethical and condemnable. The responsibility of humans is to keep the resources available for future generations to come and to hand over a healthy planet to them. But, on the contrary, we are recklessly destroying the planet and its resources, for which earthquakes, droughts, floods, landslides, and other calamities like global warming are becoming frequent and more alarming. In contemporary ethics, this question is considered a distinct area of study known as 'intergenerational ethics'. Its central tenet is that the present generation has moral responsibilities not only to themselves but also to future generations—especially concerning environmental protection, resource utilization, and climate change—because the long-term consequences of today's decisions will profoundly affect their lives, health, and opportunities. The environment is getting polluted, the lung of the planet earth - The Amazon is today burning, our oceans are getting littered with plastic, animals are dying, and the seawater level is rising due to the melting of the polar ices and so on. Not only that, now are people also seen in various disorders of diseases. Since children's birth, the skin problems, eye problems, even though the problem of respiratory problems is seen, the reason for which the balance of the ecosystem is destroyed in some way.

Therefore, man must show humanity in him and stop acting cruelly against nature, because, human beings are not something that stays outside of the ecosystem. If the ecosystem is destroyed, human beings would also be destroyed. Despite the governments having taken steps at different times regarding the duties of humans and environmental reforms, they have not been applied to work properly. It is said in the 48th article of the Indian Constitution through the 42nd amendment in 1976 that “*The State shall endeavor to protect and improve the environment and to safeguard the forests and wildlife of the country*”^{12(Nanda 518)}. Again, in the clause G of Article 51-A, it is said about the duty of a citizen regarding the environment it is said that “*It shall be the duty of every citizen of **India** to protect and improve the natural environment including forests, lakes, rivers and wildlife and to*

have compassion for living creatures”.^{13(Nanda 518)} 14th -25th June in 1993 there was organized a World Conference on Human Rights in which 171 countries took part. It was said there that

“The right to development must be fulfilled to equitably meet developmental and environmental needs of present and future generations.”^{14(Nanda 519)}

Just as the "right to a healthy environment" has gradually emerged as a fundamental human right in international human rights discussions, in the Indian context too, environmental justice is being viewed at two levels:

- (a) substantive rights: such as the right to clean air, clean water, safe forests, and biodiversity;
- (b) procedural rights: such as the right to participate in environmental decision-making, the right to information, and the opportunity to file public interest litigation on environmental issues in court. These procedural rights establish the citizen not merely as a victim, but as an active moral and legal participant.

But, still, there is not enough consciousness about the environment. We are often engrossed with self-profit. We are enjoying the natural resources neglecting sustaining development.

In 1987, the World Conference on Environment and Development (WCED, 1987) published their report entitled 'Our Common Future' which is known as the Brundtland Commission Report' after its Chair, the Prime Minister of Norway, Gro Harlem Brundtland. The report popularized the phrase 'sustainable development' and defined it as, *“development that meets the needs of the present generation without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs”*.^{15(“Brundtland Commission”)}

This definition encompasses the three fundamental pillars of sustainable development: environmental protection, economic development, and social justice. By mentioning "present needs" alongside "not compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs," the Brundtland Report demonstrated that development cannot simply be understood as increasing current

consumption; the limits of natural resources, environmental pollution, and the question of intergenerational justice must also be considered simultaneously. But we are leading our future generations to the brink of a disaster. We will not be able to protect our environment if we do not develop the Ecological Consciousness (also known as Ecological Moral Sense) in ourselves. The main duty of a man is to be conscious of his environment; to kindle his wisdom and save the environment from disaster. It does not matter how many natures protection acts we put into force in our society, unless we can love nature from within, we will not get a healthy environment.

Even though in recent times man is becoming more aware of nature and environment, as in, “*after the release of Rachel Carson’s book ‘Silent Spring’ in 1962 a fresh wave of human consciousness spread across the world, through several nature-loving organizations and other means, there remains a hidden profitability in the psyche of man*”.^{16 (Khanam 18)} Today the existence of human beings is under threat due to the decaying environment. Humans are selfish; hence, there remains a lack of consciousness about nature despite them having put into force so many laws protecting nature; and only having gained consciousness when their existence is at stake. In reality, humans want the goodness of nature because they want the goodness for them and even from that point of view protecting the ecosystem prove to be an utmost duty for them. In short, it does not matter whether you want the goodness for nature or yourself; you have to take care of the balance of the ecosystem. In other ways, we can say that we all have a duty towards protecting nature both directly and indirectly.

The consciousness of man towards nature is often adulterated. We talk about the protection of nature but we do not practice those ourselves. We talk of sustainable development but our development is unsustainable. We raise our voice against the usage of plastic bags, yet, we ask for plastic carry bags from the shopkeeper. It means, this phony environment consciousness not only does not make the environment normalcy but also pushes us

forward towards a disastrous calamity; the result of which has to be borne by us humans and the beginning of it is already underway.

However, in the Indian context, it is observed that not only the constitution and court directives, but also the distinct cultural and religious practices of various groups have fostered a kind of local environmental ethics. For example, the Bishnoi community of Rajasthan and Haryana has, for centuries, upheld the prohibition of tree felling and the killing of wild animals, considering "nature conservation" as a religious tenet; similarly, in the Chipko movement of Uttarakhand in the 1970s, hill villagers, especially many women, embraced trees (chipko) to stage a non-violent protest against commercial deforestation. These movements and practices demonstrate that "grass-roots ecological ethics" have often provided an alternative moral language for coexisting with nature, even before laws were enacted.

But, indeed, human beings cannot be made completely responsible towards nature. Again, most of the policies that were taken with the view to protect nature have proven to be failures. So, it can be said that a change in perspective is required for the government and the public alike. Such policies have to be undertaken so that the public spontaneously takes part in it. Hence, that would not only be limited to being a duty of an individual. The economical side would also be maintained. Not only the matter should be dependent on the economical side, but ethics and aesthetics also have to be taken into consideration as well. We have to bring the environment back to normalcy from the jaws of disaster and maintain the balance of our ecosystem. We have to give the environment its due respect.

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